

Effect of Replacing Soybean Meal with Flamboyant Seed Meal on the Performance of Broiler

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Abstract

The experiment was conducted to assess the effect of replacing soya beans meal with flamboyant seed meal (FSM) in broiler diets. Two Hundred and fifty (250) birds were used in the experiments. The birds were divided into five (5) groups (treatments) with fifty (50) birds per treatment and each treatment replicated five times with 10 birds per replicate. The broiler diets were prepared T1 (control), T2 (FSM 10%), T3 (FSM 20%), T4 (FSM 30%) and T5 (FSM 50%). The result show that feed intake and feed conversion ratio show that there was significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between treatments. Even though the body weight gain of T5 has the highest value of (1209.9g/b). From the result obtained in this research work it can be concluded that flamboyant seed meal could replace soya beans meal at 40% inclusion level without any effect. It was recommended that further research on this flamboyant seed meal in other livestock species. And also, proximate analysis of flamboyant seed should be done before its utilization as feed ingredient. Hematological parameters of the animals fed with diet containing different levels of flamboyant seed meal should be considered in future research.

Keywords: Soybean meal, Flamboyant seed meal, Performance, Broiler.

INTRODUCTION

Rapid increase in population growth in Nigeria indicates increasing demand for crop and livestock products, Complete reliance on traditional farming in which emphasis is on crop production can hardly sustain the nutritional requirement of the populace because of amino acid imbalance in the crop (Aduku and Olukosi, 2001). Thus, livestock production has to be intensified in order to prevent malnutrition. Poultry and other livestock are good source of protein and contain all essential amino acids required by man (Aduku, 2006). Inadequate protein intake leads to malnutrition which causes illness to man and also reduce immunity against disease. Therefore, prevention of household budgetary allocation for drug purchase during illness can be overtaken by consuming balanced diet in which animal protein cannot be left out (Aduku and Olukosi, 2001). Increase in competition for conventional feed ingredients are commonly used for compounding feed for livestock has been identified as a major reason for increasing cost of feed (Atteh, 2002). Flamboyant (*Delonix regia*) is a widely grown ornamental leguminous plant which produces pods containing reasonable quantity of seeds with moderately high crude protein (Grant *et al.*, 1999). It is a perennial tree whose abundant seed production is more or less at no specific use despite its earlier identification as a rich nutrient source by NRC (1994). Hence, the utilization of flamboyant seed as a nutrient source for livestock may reduce the cost of feeding and also increase the affordability of poultry products by man. NRC (1994).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Site

The experiment was conducted at the Poultry Unit of Department of Animal Science, College of Agriculture, Federal University of Agriculture Zuru, Kebbi State, Nigeria. The area is geographically located within latitude 11° 35' and 11° 55' N and longitude 4° 25' and 5° 25' E of the equator approximately. Zuru Local Government Area is located in the South is characterized by a single rainy season with a long dry season is between May and October. The climatic condition of the areas is characterized by hot and wet season while the month of November to January is the hamattan period (Baba *et al.*, 2013).

Source and Housing of Experimental Birds

A total of two hundred and fifty (250) day old broiler birds were used for the experiment. The broilers were sourced from Topmost Farm at Ibadan, Oyo State. The broilers were checked for deformities and unhealed naval at their arrival to the experimental site.

The birds were housed at the Poultry Unit of the Department of Animal Science, College of Agriculture. Before the arrival of the birds, the pen that was used to house the birds was thoroughly washed and disinfected with germicide (IZAL). Equipment used for feed and water supply were made available in addition to litter materials. The pen was partitioned into 25 compartments.

Experimental Diets

Five experimental diets were formulated for the birds. The ingredients used include maize, wheat bran, bone meal, limestone, premix and salt etc.

Table 1: Basal experimental diets

Parameters	T1 (0%)	T2 (10%)	T3 (20%)	T4 (30%)	T5 (40%)
Maize	65.04	66.20	63.04	54.34	50.34
SBM	20.16	10.00	7.16	5.16	0.16
FSM	0	10	20	30	40
W/Offal	10	9	5	7	5
Lysine	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Methionine	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Bone meal	1	1	1	1	1
Palm oil	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Premix	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Salt	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Limestone	2	2	2	2	2

Source, Field Experiment (2022).

Management of Experimental Birds

The birds were administered with anti-stress on their arrival at the experimental site. The birds were managed on a deep litter system while water and feed were provided *ad-libitum*. All the birds received the same treatments throughout the experiment apart from diets. The broilers were also vaccinated with ‘‘Gomboro’’ and ‘‘NDV lasota’’ against Newcastle and Infectious bursal disease respectively.

Experimental Design

The experimental design used for the research was completely randomized design (CRD). The birds were randomly grouped into five treatments and each treatment was further grouped into five replicate at which each group comprising fifty (50) birds. Each group received different experimental diets that served as the treatments for the experiment.

Data Collection

The birds were weighed at the onset of experiment and subsequently, on weekly basis for eight weeks. Daily feed intake of the birds was also monitored for duration of eight weeks. Feed conversion ratio was evaluated using body weight gain and feed intake.

Statistical Analysis

Data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA). SPSS software was used to determine the significant difference at 5% ($P < 0.05$), the means was separated by Duncan’s multiple range test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initial weight per bird show no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) across the treatments. Final body weight did not differ significantly ($P > 0.05$) across the treatments. Even though T5 recorded the highest final weight of 1890 gram per bird g/b compared to other treatments T1, T2, T3 and T4 recorded a final weight of 1700, 1750.04, 1790.10 and 1810.13 respectively.

Feed intake per bird differs significantly ($P < 0.05$) (Table 2) as birds fed T5 recorded the highest feed intake of 3269 (g/b) and T1 has the least value of feed intake (3200 g/b). Feed intake per bird/day shows a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) across the treatments. Birds fed T5 recorded the highest value of feed intake g/b/d of 58.37.

Body weight gain g/b observed significance ($P < 0.05$) (Table 2) difference between the treatments. Even though birds in T5 has a highest value of (1850 g/b) compared to the value recorded for T1, T2, T3 and T4 for 1660.05, 1710.04, 1750.1 and 1770.13 respectively. The feed conversion ratio shows significant difference ($P < 0.05$) among the treatments as the best value was recorded in T₅ (1.94) (Table 2).

Table 2: Effect of replacing soya bean meal with flamboyant seed meal in broiler diet

Parameters	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	SEM
Initial body weight (g/b)	40.00	40.00	40.00	40.00	40.00	0.00
Final body weight (g/b)	1700.05 ^b	1750.04 ^b	1790.10 ^b	1810.13 ^a	1890.00 ^a	92.00
Feed intake (g/b)	3200	3250	3260	3266	3269	21.29
Feed intake (g/b/d)	57.14 ^a	58.03 ^c	58.21 ^b	58.32 ^a	58.37 ^c	3.91
Body weight gain (g/b)	1660.05 ^c	1710.04 ^b	1750.1 ^b	1770.13 ^b	1850 ^a	92.85
Body weight gain (g/b/d)	29.64 ^c	30.53 ^b	31.25 ^b	31.60 ^b	33.03 ^a	1.65
Mortality (%)	0.75	0.00	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.19
Feed conversion ratio	2.0 ^a	1.90 ^a	1.86 ^a	1.84 ^a	1.76 ^b	0.14

This study investigated the effect of replacing soya beans meal with flamboyant seed meal in broilers diet. The feed intake in the present study show no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) across the treatments, this finding is in line with report of Young and Mukherjee (2003) who fed broiler with flamboyant seed meal.

The body weight of broilers observed showed no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) in weight gain as SBM was replaced with FSM in the diets of broilers as reported by Badifu, (1993). Flamboyant seed meal can replace soya beans meal without any effect and his result showed there was no significant difference in body weight gain ($P > 0.05$). This result agree with the earlier finding of OKendo *et al.* (2005) who reported that better performance ($P < 0.05$) of broilers fed either GNC or FSM compared to those fed SBM alone.

Feed conversion ratio is a direct indication of how best the feed given to birds is turned to meat. In this experiment, birds fed 50% inclusion level of FSM gave the best FCR ($P < 0.05$) in converting feed to gain.

In this experiment mortality was recorded in T₁ and T₃ which falls within the acceptable range of 0-5% for good management practices (ISA, 1996).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the result obtained in this research work it can be concluded that flamboyant seed meal could replace soya beans meal at 40% inclusion level without any effect.

In view of the result obtained it can be suggested that:

- Base on the above experiment, extension workers are therefore call open to highlight the farmers on the positive effect of flamboyant seed meal on broiler production so as to reduce the cost production.
- It also recommended to further research on this flamboyant seed meal in other livestock species.
- Hematological parameters of the animals fed with diet containing different levels of flamboyant seed meal should be considered in future research.

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